

THE INFLUENCE OF GROWTH REGULATORS ON THE FORMATION OF THE PRODUCTIVITY OF CULTIVATED CARROTS IN THE STEPPE OF UKRAINE

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Due to its high nutritional value, economic efficiency, and medicinal and dietary properties, carrots are one of the leading vegetable crops, second only to cabbage and potatoes [1].

The popularity of carrots is explained by their rich chemical composition: carotenoids (dominated by β -carotene), vitamins (C, E, K, B), and minerals (potassium, calcium, phosphorus, iron, and iodine), which help strengthen the immune system, reduce cardiovascular disease, and improve the digestive system.

Thanks to their ability to provide stable yields when technological requirements are met, carrots occupy an important place in the structure of vegetable production in the Ukrainian Steppe. This crop is highly adaptable to regional conditions, provided that the soil is adequately moisturized and balanced nutrition is available. The deep root system allows it to effectively absorb moisture and nutrients from the lower soil layers. Carrots play an important role in crop rotation, helping to improve soil structure and interrupting the development cycle of many pests and diseases.

During periods of moisture deficiency and the threat of high temperatures, risks arise for the formation of high-quality root crop yields, requiring solutions that increase plant stress resistance and productivity. One such solution is the introduction of growth regulators into cultivation technology. They influence the processes of germination, vegetation, root formation, and ripening, which contributes to increased yields and improved commercial and quality characteristics of products [2].

Growth regulators also reduce the damage to root crops caused by late blight and other diseases, including fungal infections. This makes it possible to improve the realization of yield potential even in unfavorable years, which is particularly important for the Steppe regions. In addition, studies show that the use of such regulators has a positive effect on the preservation of quality and shelf life of root crops [3].

The effect of growth regulators depends on the variety. This is due to the genetic characteristics of each variety, such as the rate of leaf and root system development and the ability to redistribute assimilates.

During the research, our goal was to determine the effect of growth regulators on the productivity of carrots in the conditions of the Northern Steppe of Ukraine. The research was conducted using the growth regulators Razormin and Raikat Rise on the carrot varieties Shantane and Nantes, by spraying the plants during the growing season at a rate of 0.5 l/ha. The results of the research show that the use of growth regulators on carrot crops significantly activated the physiological and biochemical processes in plants. This contributed to improved initial growth, the formation of a developed leaf surface, and an increase in the intensity of root biomass accumulation.

Thus, growth regulators show promise in increasing the yield and quality of carrots in the steppe conditions of Ukraine, especially during periods of unfavorable weather conditions.

References

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